

Ir00000014 – Itserr

TransNational Access Management Plan (TNA_MP)

Document reference: ITSERR-WP11-D11.1-TNA_MP
Version number: 01.00
Status: FINAL
Last revision date: 17/07/2024 by: UNIPA
Verification date: 28/11/2022 by: Board
Approval date: DD/MM/YYYY by: MUR
Subject: IR00000014 – ITSERR
TransNational Access Management Plan (TNA_MP)
Filename ITSERR_WP11_D11.1_TNA_MP_01.00_FINAL.docx

*This research has been funded by the Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR)
Mission 4 – Component 2 under the project ITSERR Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE*

CUP B53C22001770006 Ir00000014

Change history

Version Number	Date	Status	Summary of main or important changes
00.01	25/11/2022	WORKING	Working version
00.02	03/05/2024	DRAFT	Draft
00.03	10/06/2024	DRAFT	Draft
01.00	17/07/2024	FINAL	Final version after MoU with RESILIENCE

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This document is available in the ITSERR WP Management document repository at:
ITSERR-4WPs_Deliverables\D11.1_TNA Management Plan\

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1. Document overview

Objectives

The Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (MUR) has concluded a Grant Agreement (GA) with the ITSER consortium (ITSERR₁) for the provision of IT services to support the existing national infrastructure and bring it to a higher level of maturity, in terms of involvement of technology and ability to increase the innovation, quality and variety of the knowledge produced by the community of Religious Studies.

Through its funded **Transnational Access Programme** ITSERR offers support and expertise for research stays at leading Italian Universities and research centres holding relevant collections within libraries and archives for Religious Studies together with outstanding IT laboratories for the increasing of the development of Digital Humanities. Moreover, the programme allows to support research stays of the ITSERR members within the network of hosts of RESILIENCE through the calls for proposals of this RI.

The TNA ITSERR funded programme will provide to its community of researchers the following facilities:

physical and virtual access to data, structures and expertise

physical and virtual access to the most significant tools and sources in the field of Religious Studies and IT laboratories

This document is the TNA Management Plan (TNA_MP) for the Grant and represents the reference document by which ITSERR demonstrates that it can represent a case-study for research-enhancing services and habits within the wider framework of the Religious Studies and related disciplines, including multidisciplinary and multilingual research.

The major purposes of this TNA_MP are: the description of the organization of the programme and its shared vision (purposes and procedures) with RESILIENCE, but also the description of the access policy and the criteria of excellence of it, in relationship with TNA hosts and users. The TNA MP defines their rights and duties within the program together with a system of monitoring procedures and providing the necessary information to accomplish some of the main goals of the project about the RI.

Scope

This TNA Management Plan covers exclusively the GA organisational bodies:

ITSERR

as defined in the Grant Agreement IR00000014 - ITSERR (see applicable document [A2]).

This TNA_MP is to be applied by each staff employed on the WP and to all work performed within it. It is a binding document being part of the contractual documents. In case of misinterpretation or conflicts, the Grant Agreement Contract and its annexes have precedence over this document.

2. Physical and virtual access

The combination of physical and virtual access to data is essential for comprehensive multidisciplinary and multilingual research in Religious Studies. In this sense, physical and virtual access to the infrastructure is at the core of ITSERR and encompasses sources, resources, expertise and services relevant for Religious Studies provided by the distributed facilities, whose impact could shape the scenery of research within this fieldwork.

However, physical access of ITSERR TNA is finalized to enjoy the environment of Universities and Research Centers dedicated to Humanities, Digital Humanities and IT.

Moreover, in many cases collections and documents have not been digitised yet (or it is not possible to digitise them) and are preserved in libraries and archives in different countries, which makes physical access a necessity for the community of users.

Also, some of the digital resources held by the facilities can in certain cases only be accessed on site, usually due to property rights. Furthermore, physical access to IT laboratories allows them to approach new methodologies and instruments - thanks to the expertise a key-element of the TNA - by increasing cooperation between researchers and definitely it improves the networking.

Virtual access concerns the collection of all the documents digitally available, the born-digital and digitally transformed data within a single and distributed ecosystem to make them eventually available also remotely. Moreover, by supporting the mobility of scholars who need to conduct their research on the resources consulted onsite - physical and digital - the project contributes to the digitization of resources by having a long-lasting and visible impact on the research quality of the Religious Studies research community.

Physical and virtual access within the ITSERR consortium

ITSERR consortium and partners answer the need of physical access with different physical service layers:

- 1) The partners give access to the facilities of their GLAM sector (especially libraries, e-libraries, archives and special collections relevant to Religious Studies' research) together with IT laboratories.
- 2) The access to specialized centers offers to researchers' multiple opportunities, such as active participation in Research Seminars by presenting their research results and step into an interdisciplinary dialogue. Specialized Research Centres, Digital Humanities Centres and IT laboratories provide expertise in relevant fields.

3) Funded fellowships of ITSERR TNA support international scholars to access the resources physically available at the distributed facilities.

The aim of ITSERR is to facilitate and foster a sophisticated and advanced Trans-National Access (TNA) system to sources, resources, expertise and services for researchers in Religious Studies and related disciplines which are available at the distributed facilities, ensure an efficient access workflow and a single entry point (ITSERR homepage and central helpdesk). In order to cover as many disciplines involved in the study of religions in all their facets as possible and provide the widest range of relevant materials and expertise, ITSERR seeks to include further partners in its TNA programme as one of the outcomes shared with the RI RESILIENCE.

3. ITSERR TNA funded programme

ITSERR TNA represents a concrete service for the development and enhancing of the research in Religious Studies by offering the possibility to the TNA fellows to organize their stay within the ITSERR partners facilities and it allows also to the research members of the consortium to organize their stay within the network of hosts of RESILIENCE through the calls for proposals of this RI.

The programme is funded by NextGenerationEU - National Recovery and Resilience Plan (Piano Nazionale di Ripresa e Resilienza, PNRR), and it allows scholars or teams researching on Religious Studies to spend approximately from 1 week to 1 month at one of the ITSERR Italian nodes of the project and benefit from their facilities. The funded TNA for teams is a specific feature of ITSERR, as it gives the opportunity for a collaborative improvement of knowledge between research teams from different countries.

ITSERR TNA funded programme foresees **ingoing** and **outgoing mobility**, thanks to a shared system of call for applications with RESILIENCE TNA:

Foreign scholars (European and non-European) and PhD students – **individuals or teams** – within the fieldwork of Religious Studies or within the fieldwork of IT for DH - can apply for funded TNA within the nodes of the **ITSERR network (ingoing mobility)** through the call for applications of the present programme and through the ones of the RESILIENCE RI.

ITSERR scholars and PhD students from programs of the ITSERR consortium can apply for funded TNA within the framework of the **RESILIENCE TNA calls** to stay in one of the TNA Hosts of the RESILIENCE RI (**outgoing mobility**) <https://www.resilience-ri.eu/cfa-tna/>

Through of this shared system of call for applications - according to what established by the MoU between ITSERR and RESILIENCE, ITSERR can offer three own calls for applications (June 2024; December 2024; June 2025) and 2 calls for applications of RESILIENCE TNA (October 2024; March 2025).

However, the funded TNA for teams is a specific feature of ITSERR, as it gives the opportunity for a collaborative improvement of knowledge between interdisciplinary research teams from different countries and this specific TNA it will be available only within the Italian network of hosts of ITSERR.

In order to provide excellence-driven access to its physical and digital resources, ITSERR offers funded TNA for qualified researchers (120 weeks for individual – **50 users** – 108 months for teams **25 users**) seeking to conduct a research visit at one of the partner facilities.

The goal of the research visits is to grant scholars a direct, fast and effective access to the objects of their research. This includes access to research material and instructions to effectively make use of it as well as a workplace at the facility. Furthermore, ITSERR aims at matching all successful TNA applicants with experts at the facilities to have access to relevant expertise.

Users will receive scientific as well as administrative and logistic support to conduct their research stay as efficiently as possible. They will receive all necessary guidance and training to access the resources purposefully and may receive scientific advice from experts in their respective field of

research. Users can get access to research seminars and workshops and the opportunity to present their research.

ITSERR TNA covers all kinds of facilities of travel, accommodation and subsistence costs for selected users.

Selection of access requests depends on scientific excellence, originality, quality and feasibility of the applications and is based on the ITSERR access process and modalities described below. Selection of research proposals is based on principles of non-discrimination and transparency. Upon selection, users get access to the ITSERR facilities and their resources and services. This access mode is intended to foster collaborative research, knowledge transfer, training and best practice, and scientific innovation efforts across geographical and disciplinary boundaries.

In order to design a feasible and efficient selection process, ITSERR beneficiates of RESILIENCE extensive experience from the TNA scholarship programme and its deep connection with the starting community ReIReS10 as well as best practises developed by the existing RIs of this network.

4. Application and Selection Process for TNA funded programme

The graphic below allows to visualize all the steps connected to the workflow of the system of TNA call for proposals until the evaluation of TNA.

For an efficient implementation of the scholarship programme, the TNA Unit (led by University of Palermo and collaborating with the other Italian partnership of the RI) will coordinate the whole process from communicating the programme to its evaluation:

advertises scholarship programme (prepares the call for proposals, coordinates its publication, including guide for applicants and selection criteria),

collects and processes the application forms received,

ordinates selection and ranking process,

collects and processes applications,

checks eligibility of submissions,

coordinates selection and ranking process,

Moreover, TNA officer will coordinate:

- Arrangement of the visit of the selected users in advance: Planning of time slots; ensuring that materials and experts are available; booking tickets, rooms.
- Support of the research during the stay of the user; arrangement of meetings with experts and tutorials.

- Communication with facilities/partner libraries about holdings, access to materials, digital tools, research etc.
- Ensure that all ITSERR TNA users fill in the evaluation questionnaire;

Call for proposals

ITSERR will launch three own calls for proposals for the TNA funded programme, starting on the 30th of June 2024, the other two are planned for December 2024 and June 2025.

Each call for proposals contains the detailed description of the opportunities, expertise and services that ITSERR offers as well as instructions for applications.

Calls for proposals, application forms and other supporting documents and materials are made available on the ITSERR website. The ITSERR website provides all information on the University Departments and Research Centers involved as well as access conditions and processes.

Each call will be advertised on the same website of ITSERR – within the webpage dedicated to it (<https://www.itserr.it/index.php/itserr-tna/cfa-tna/>) - and through the website and social media channels used by RESILIENCE (LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, Instagram), on communication channels of the partners and on relevant portals and online journals for Theology, Religious Studies and Humanities as well as RI-related but also public mailing lists.

The ITSERR website will be implemented with all information for users on access procedures and on the facilities providing access. Rules and conditions of the access process will be stated clearly and precisely, and will be as easy as possible, to facilitate the access of users to the RI services.

The TNA Unit – through the e-mail address tna@itserr.it - will act as a helpdesk supporting researchers in the development of the proposals, offering answers to potential user requests and giving assistance with the submission procedure in order to avoid mistakes and encourage candidatures.

Finally, as stated through the MoU with RESILIENCE, the five ITSERR Consortium members will join the RESILIENCE TNA Hosting network no later than **1 October 2024**.

MOUs will run until 31 May 2026 where this can be agreed upon with the individual institutes, and otherwise until 31 October 2025.

ITSERR will provide the information for the RESILIENCE TNA website to create separate TNA Host webpages.

ITSERR will appoint a TNA Coordinator per institute to guarantee the practicalities of each RESILIENCE TNA visit.

RESILIENCE will arrange for a TNA Hosting training for all five institutes to prepare all the necessary to join as hosts within the RESILIENCE call for proposals.

Applications

All applications must be in English and submitted via the application form provided by the ITSERR website.

- Name
- E-mail
- Institution
- Country
- Relevant publications of the applicant
- Indication of the intended hosting facility
- Indication of the duration of access
- Abstract of the project
- Description of the project as well as the research material and expertise required

The webpage dedicated to TNA call for proposals allows users to download a specific application form to fill in each field and which includes all the relevant information for the evaluation. Within the application must be included as a 2 pages CV.

Selection and Ranking Procedure

The selection and ranking procedure is achieved through the use of two Boards: the Access Board (ACB) that reviews the feasibility and the ITSERR Peer Review Committee (PRC) that makes decisions about the selection and the ranking of the applications.

Within the TNA call for proposals of ITSERR, according to the specific features of ITSERR project and due to the high scientific quality of the TNA coordinators of each venue of the consortium, the ABC and the PRC will be composed by the same members although in some cases of evaluation of the applications these can be submitted to an external member for his expertise on a subject.

Within the TNA call for proposals of RESILIENCE – according to the MoU to become hosts within the European RI TNA programme - our boards will review applications for ITSERR Institutions by following RESILIENCE reviews criteria and procedures.

ITSERR Access Board

The ITSERR Access Board consists of the representatives from each partner facility providing access to physical resources. It provides support to users

- Checks feasibility of the submissions (timing, availability of sources/experts),
- Offers feedback to the Physical Access Unit concerning the quality of the research visit and identifies possible contingencies concerning the access provision,
- Advises the Physical Access Unit about the quality and impact of the communication, dissemination and exploitation of the results of the project, helping in identifying the most efficient and effective solutions.
- Reports to the Physical Access Unit, confirms that the access took place and indicates the number of access units granted.

ITSERR Peer Review Committee (PRC)

The PRC conducts the selection and ranking of submitted proposals which are both eligible and feasible. Its work is based on principles of transparency, fairness and impartiality.

The PRC meets via online conference by one month after the application deadlines and after each meeting provides a detailed and appropriate report ranking the approved applications and their classification in order of priority, addressing this document to the Access Board and the TNA Unit.

The applications are stored in a secured online repository that only provides access to authorised members of ACB and the PRC due to its nature of personal and sensitive data such as rejections with justification and assessments of scientific quality. All personal data will be deleted up to six months after the submission of the application.

The ITSERR Peer Review Committee consists of internal members of high scientific quality and experience and, in some specific cases, of external members (ensuring gender balance among PRC members) and oversees the scholarly review and ranking of the applications. The internal members are members of the TNA Unit, while the external members can be involved for their internationally acknowledged expertise in the fields of Religious Studies and IT Technologies. The external members are selected by the TNA Unit and the Access Board. The Unit members chair the activities of the Committee and coordinate its operation, taking care of the documentation of its activities.

Selection and Ranking Criteria

- Research quality of the proposal (0–10 points)
- Originality of the research activity (0–10 points)
- Level of expertise of the potential user (0–10 points)
- Connection between the research project and the researches led by the ITSERR WPs (0–10 points)
- Potential of the research project (0–10 points)
- The project has European impact (0–10 points)

- Coherence between the research project and the timeline to develop it (0-10 points)

In case of equal qualifications regarding the criteria above, priority is given to applications which fulfil these criteria:

The project has a woman group leader or principal investigator, or the gender balance within the group members is fulfilled, or it includes a specific focus on gender issues (yes/no)

- The project is led by a young scholar who aims to significantly improve his training in humanities and particularly in Religious Studies (yes/no)
- The project is proposed by a user who belongs to a country where no research infrastructure or research platform in Religious Studies exists (yes/no)
- The project is proposed by a user who has no previous access to the RI partner facility applied for (yes/no)
- The project requires a strong integration between the access to special collections and the use of digital tools (yes/no)

The PRC develops an evaluation procedure according to internationally accepted standards. On the basis of this evaluation and the resulting ranking of the applications, the candidates are selected and will be received by the respective institutions.

The representatives of the facilities are in charge of giving notification about the status of their application based on the ranking. They invite selected users and coordinate their research visit. The Physical Access Unit oversees the communication.

5. Post-Access Provisions

ITSERR will establish post-access provisions in order to record the scientific output of the users resulting from the access and to establish feedback mechanisms where users can report their access experience, in order to improve the RI services, and for self-evaluation.

Within 30 days after the funded research visit, the user must fill in a user questionnaire (to be set up in the Preparatory Phase), this is mandatory for the reimbursement of the expenses incurred during the research visit.

Users are asked to provide information on objectives, methods, preliminary results of the TNA, as well as the management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated during their project.

ITSERR ensures to store and host digitised data and digital-born research data by FAIR- by- design or in a FAIR-compliant way. The user questionnaire allows us to assess the quality of the provided access.

Users are requested to acknowledge the RI and the use of the facility and the contribution of those persons working at the ITSERR facilities. In line with good scientific practice, they are encouraged to offer co- authorship to those working in the RI having made genuine scientific contributions to their

work. RI users are encouraged to publish their research results gained through the TNA electronically and according to Open Access principles.

6. Training

Through its Access Policy, ITSERR offers an innovative programme of training activities based on the effective necessities of the researchers.

Training during TNA is finalized to enhance the skills required for groundbreaking research in Religious Studies in terms of methodological, historical and linguistic knowledge, IT methodologies and procedures as well as scholarly contributions from other disciplines.

The training is offered on demand for different user groups which will be defined individually based on the contents of the training.

This specific feature of training is based on the necessities and expectative of the researchers and connected to the expertise present in each center of the ITSERR consortium.

Moreover, the researchers will be informed on the activities led in each center during their stays (such as conferences, seminars and workshops) and they will be encouraged to participate in them. Whereby ITSERR is aiming to try to meet the users' demands. Details of the selection process are defined from case to case.

7. Applicable documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[A1]	20/03/2019	H2020-INFRADEV-2018-2020, (Development and long-term sustainability of new pan-European research infrastructures), Proposal number: 871127-2
[A2]		GRANT AGREEMENT, NUMBER — IR00000014 — ITSERR
[A3]	To be Released	Data Management Plan

All documents mentioned in this list are available in the Document Repository, section "Applicable Documents".

8. Reference documents

Applicable documents are documents from which all requirements must be fulfilled in the context of the Grant Agreement, although they are not repeated in the present document.

Id.	Date	Title / Reference
[R1]	25/11/2022	Detailed Organisational Plan

9. Acronyms

A list of acronyms frequently used in this document is available below:

Term	Definition
CO	Collaborator of a PI (Principal Investigator)
FO	Financial Officer
GA	Grant Agreement
IAB	International Advisory Board
IB	ITSERR Board
IB members	General Assembly
IM	Infrastructure Manager
ITSERR	Italian Strengthening of the ESFRI RI RESILIENCE
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MUR	Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca
OU	Organisational Unit
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PI	Principal Investigator
PLA	Performance Level Agreement
PRC	Peer Review Committee
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SSF	Stakeholders Strategic Forum
TNA	Trans-National Access
VA	Virtual Access